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Women's Roles in Agricultural Decision-Making: A Case Study of Federal Ministries and Women Farmers' Groups in FCT

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ABSTRACT

This study examines women's roles in agricultural decision-making in Nigeria, focusing on Federal Line Ministries and Women Farmers' Organisations in Abuja (FCT). Agriculture remains central to Nigeria's economy, yet gender-based inequalities continue to limit women's participation and recognition in governance processes. Women contribute substantially to planting, harvesting, and post-harvest activities but remain underrepresented in formal agricultural policy and decision-making structures. Using a mixed-methods approach and multi-stage sampling of 318 respondents—including policymakers, women farmers, extension workers, and NGO representatives—the study provides both quantitative and qualitative insights into women's engagement. Findings reveal that most respondents are aware of federal involvement in agricultural governance and that women participate in national-level decision-making, thereby promoting agricultural growth, poverty reduction, and sustainable development. However, barriers such as socio-cultural norms, limited access to resources, lack of education, and underrepresentation in leadership constrain women's full participation. The study also highlights a need for greater awareness of policies and programs that support women's inclusion. Encouragingly, gender-inclusive policies are increasingly being implemented in the FCT. The study recommends gender impact assessments and mandatory 30–40% representation of women in agricultural boards, cooperatives, and rural development committees to foster equitable participation and policy influence.

Keywords: Women Farmers, Agricultural Decision-Making, Gender Equality, Federal Ministries, Sustainable Development

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Agriculture remains the backbone of Nigeria's economy, contributing significantly to employment, food security, and rural livelihoods (Musa et al., 2025). Within this sector, women play an indispensable role as farmers, processors, traders, and household food providers (Muhammed et al., 2025). Despite their

substantial contributions to agricultural production, women often face systemic barriers that limit their participation in decision-making processes for agricultural planning, land use, resource allocation, and marketing (Doss, 2011; Food and Agriculture Organisation [FAO], 2011; Magaji, 2002). In sub-Saharan Africa, women contribute nearly 60% of agricultural labour. However, their access to productive assets, credit, and extension services remains disproportionately low compared to men (World Bank, FAO, & International Fund for Agricultural Development [IFAD], 2009; Magaji & Mohammed, 2004). This gender imbalance not only affects women's productivity but also undermines efforts toward achieving sustainable agricultural development. Therefore, understanding women's roles in agricultural decision-making, particularly within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), is critical for achieving gender equality and economic inclusiveness in Nigeria's agricultural sector.

Women's participation in agricultural decision-making encompasses their involvement in determining what crops to plant, managing household resources, controlling income, and engaging in collective actions through cooperatives and farmers' groups (Quisumbing & Pandolfelli, 2010; Olusola et al., 2025). However, traditional norms and patriarchal structures continue to influence women's access to decision-making spaces at both household and institutional levels (Agarwal, 1994; Alkire et al., 2013). Many women farmers in Nigeria, including those in the FCT, encounter structural inequalities in land tenure systems, access to inputs, and membership in agricultural associations. The persistence of such constraints reflects a broader gendered power dynamic that undermines women's agency and voice in agricultural governance. Nevertheless, emerging evidence suggests that when women are actively involved in agricultural decision-making, there are measurable improvements in household welfare, productivity, and food security outcomes (FAO, 2011; Doss, 2011).

At the institutional level, the role of federal ministries and governmental agencies in promoting women's participation in agriculture cannot be overemphasised. Ministries such as the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) and the Federal Ministry of Women Affairs (FMWA) have developed gender-sensitive policies and programs to enhance women's access to agricultural resources and leadership opportunities (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2006). However, the implementation and coordination of these initiatives have often been limited by bureaucratic challenges, inadequate funding, and insufficient stakeholder collaboration (World Bank, 2018). Women farmers' groups in the FCT have emerged as vital platforms for mobilisation, advocacy, and capacity building, yet their engagement with policy-making institutions remains weak. Bridging the gap between women farmers' organisations and government institutions is essential to create participatory frameworks that enable women's voices to influence agricultural decision-making processes at local and national levels.

Furthermore, agricultural decision-making is multidimensional, encompassing both individual and collective agency. While household-level decisions often reflect gendered divisions of labour and control over resources, community- and institutional-level decision-making involves engagement with cooperatives, NGOs, and ministries responsible for agricultural development (Quisumbing & Maluccio, 2003; Meinzen-Dick et al., 2011). In the context of the FCT, the coexistence of federal institutions and active women's farmers' associations presents a unique opportunity to examine how national agricultural policies are implemented and how women's groups navigate institutional structures to assert their decision-making power. Understanding these interactions is essential for evaluating the effectiveness of gender-responsive agricultural policies and for identifying strategies to enhance women's participation in governance and planning processes related to agriculture.

This study, therefore, seeks to explore women's roles in agricultural decision-making by examining the interplay between federal ministries and women's farmers' groups in the FCT. It investigates the extent to which women are included in decision-making processes, the institutional mechanisms that support or hinder their participation, and the socio-economic factors influencing their level of involvement. The study's significance lies in its potential to inform gender-responsive agricultural policies that promote inclusivity, enhance productivity, and support sustainable agricultural transformation in Nigeria. By amplifying the voices of women farmers and strengthening institutional collaboration, this research

contributes to the broader discourse on gender equality, empowerment, and sustainable agricultural development in sub-Saharan Africa.

2.0 Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Agricultural Decision-Making

Agricultural decision-making refers to the processes by which farmers, households, and institutions make choices about agricultural activities, such as crop selection, resource allocation, land use, input use, marketing, and income management. It encompasses both individual and collective decisions that shape the efficiency and sustainability of agricultural systems (Doss, 2011). The process is influenced by various factors, including access to information, credit, technology, extension services, and prevailing socio-cultural norms (Quisumbing & Maluccio, 2003; Abubakar *et al.*, 2025). In many developing countries, agricultural decision-making is often dominated by men due to traditional gender roles, land tenure systems, and unequal access to productive resources (FAO, 2011). However, research has shown that when women are actively involved in agricultural decision-making, farm productivity and household welfare outcomes tend to improve significantly (Quisumbing & Pandolfelli, 2010). Therefore, understanding the dynamics of agricultural decision-making is vital for designing inclusive policies that promote gender equality and enhance overall agricultural performance.

2.1.2 Women Farmers

Women farmers are those actively engaged in agricultural production, processing, and marketing, whether as independent producers, family labourers, or members of farming cooperatives. Globally, women make up about 43% of the agricultural labour force, with even higher proportions in sub-Saharan Africa, where they play essential roles in ensuring household food security and rural development (FAO, 2011). Despite their critical contributions, women farmers often face systemic challenges, including limited access to land, credit, agricultural inputs, and extension services (World Bank, FAO, & IFAD, 2009). Socio-cultural barriers, institutional biases, and climate change further restrict their participation in leadership and decision-making processes within agricultural organisations (Agarwal, 1994; Yakubu *et al.*, 2025). Empowering women farmers through equitable access to resources and participatory governance not only promotes gender equality but also enhances productivity, reduces poverty, and strengthens food systems' resilience (Alkire *et al.*, 2013). Recognising the role of women farmers is, therefore, fundamental to achieving sustainable agricultural development and inclusive economic growth.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 The Empowerment Theory

The Empowerment Theory is highly relevant to this study as it provides a framework for understanding how women's participation in agricultural decision-making enhances their control over resources, agency, and overall well-being. The theory emphasises the process through which individuals and groups gain the ability to make choices, exercise power, and influence outcomes that affect their lives (Zimmerman, 2000). In the context of agriculture, empowerment involves improving women's access to productive assets such as land (Mukhtar *et al.*, 2025), credit (Chinedu *et al.*, 2021), technology and information (John *et al.*, 2025), and their inclusion in leadership and policy formulation (Kabeer, 1999). Applying the Empowerment Theory to women farmers in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) highlights how institutional support from federal ministries, combined with active participation in farmers' groups, can strengthen women's decision-making capacities and socio-economic status. This theoretical perspective underscores the interlinkage between sustainable agricultural development and gender equality: empowering women enhances productivity, promotes equity, and fosters community resilience (Alkire *et al.*, 2013). Thus, the Empowerment Theory serves as a lens through which the study examines how institutional and social mechanisms both contribute to and constrain women's roles in agricultural decision-making.

2.3 Empirical Review

Obayelu, Jimmy, and Ojo (2024) conducted a study to examine the impact of women's empowerment in agriculture on household food insecurity in Nigeria using data from the 2018/2019 Nigeria General

Household Survey. The study employed the Abbreviated Women's Empowerment in Agriculture Index (A-WEAI) and the Household Hunger Scale (HHS) to assess women's empowerment status and its effect on food security outcomes. The findings revealed that approximately 93.4% of women were disempowered, with empowerment strongly associated with reduced household food insecurity by about four percentage points. The study further indicated that households headed by women and those with higher literacy levels were less likely to experience severe hunger. This research underscores the importance of empowering women to enhance their decision-making roles in agriculture and reduce food insecurity, providing a strong justification for examining women's agricultural decision-making processes within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT).

Ifeanyi-Obi (2023) explored how rural women crop farmers in Southern Nigeria make agricultural decisions related to climate change adaptation. Using a mixed-methods approach involving surveys of 420 women farmers, focus group discussions, and key informant interviews, the study identified major adaptation strategies, including soil and crop management, the application of indigenous knowledge, and financial practices. The results showed that about 81% of respondents actively engaged in adaptation decisions, yet faced significant challenges, including inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, and limited government support. These findings demonstrate that while women exercise agency in agricultural decision-making, structural and institutional barriers significantly hinder their ability to exercise full autonomy. This evidence supports the need for examining how institutional frameworks and women's farmer groups in the FCT can enhance women's empowerment in decision-making processes.

A World Bank (2022/2023) technical report on Gender Gaps in Agriculture Productivity and Public Spending in Nigeria analysed nationally representative data from the 2018–2019 Nigeria General Household Survey. The report found that women farmers were significantly less likely to manage plots and had yields approximately 30% lower than those managed by men. The gender productivity gap was attributed to limited access to inputs, extension services, and land ownership. The report also highlighted that these disparities result in billions of dollars in lost agricultural output annually. Notably, the study emphasised the role of gender-equitable budgeting and public investment in addressing these challenges. This report provides macro-level evidence that government policies and institutional actions directly shape women's participation in agricultural decision-making, an essential focus for the FCT case study.

Ewepu (2023) reported a field-level empirical intervention in Abuja, where over 30 women farmers in Jiwa community benefited from a non-governmental organisation (NGO)-led capacity-building program on agritech, mobile finance, and market linkages. The program, organised by the Coalition for Advancement of Agriculture in Africa (CAAID), DICE, and the Smallholder Women Farmers Organisation in Nigeria (SWOFON), aimed to enhance digital inclusion and innovation among women farmers. Findings from the training showed improved knowledge of digital marketing, financial literacy, and record-keeping, thereby strengthening women's capacity to make informed agricultural decisions. Although this intervention was localised, it highlights the growing role of NGOs and community-based organisations in supplementing government efforts to empower women in agriculture, especially within the FCT.

East-West Seed Knowledge Transfer (2025) conducted a nationwide study titled *Women Farmers: Nigeria Study Report*, employing mixed-methods, including surveys, key informant interviews, and case studies, to assess women's roles in agricultural decision-making across vegetable value chains. The study revealed that women play critical roles in seed selection, crop management, and marketing, but continue to face gender-specific constraints, including restricted access to land, financial services, and quality inputs. The report also found that targeted training and extension services significantly improved women's technical decision-making abilities and self-efficacy in agriculture. The findings underscore the need for institutionalised capacity-building programs to enhance women's empowerment and participation in agricultural policy-making, aligning closely with the objectives of examining women farmers' decision-making in the FCT.

2.4 Research Gap

Although several recent studies (Obayelu et al., 2024; Ifeanyi-Obi, 2023; World Bank, 2022/2023; Ewepu, 2023; East-West Seed Knowledge Transfer, 2025) have provided valuable insights into women's empowerment and participation in agricultural activities across Nigeria, there remains a significant gap concerning the institutional and policy dimensions of women's agricultural decision-making, particularly within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Most existing research focuses on women's access to resources, productivity levels, and adaptation strategies. However, it gives limited attention to how federal ministries, agricultural institutions, and organised women's farmers' groups influence women's ability to make and implement key agricultural decisions. Additionally, while the reviewed studies highlight gender disparities in access to land, finance, and technology, they rarely examine the interaction between policy implementation, institutional frameworks, and collective action mechanisms that could enhance women's voice in decision-making. Therefore, this study addresses this critical gap by exploring the role of government institutions and women farmers' associations in strengthening women's participation and influence in agricultural decision-making within the FCT—offering a contextualised understanding of empowerment through institutional engagement and governance processes.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This section outlines the methodological framework adopted for the study, which investigates women's roles in agricultural decision-making within federal ministries and women farmers' organisations in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. It describes the research design, study area, target population, sampling methods, data collection instruments, analytical procedures, and ethical considerations. The methodological approach was designed to ensure a rigorous, systematic, and ethically grounded process for generating valid and reliable data consistent with the research objectives.

3.2 Research Design

The study adopted a mixed-methods approach, integrating quantitative and qualitative methods to examine women's participation in agricultural decision-making comprehensively. A sequential explanatory design was employed, beginning with quantitative data collection via questionnaires, followed by qualitative data collection through focus group discussions (FGDs) and in-depth interviews. This design facilitated a robust understanding of the interactions between women farmers, federal ministries, and agricultural organisations. Respondents included female farmers, government officials (particularly from the Federal Ministries of Agriculture and Food Security, Livestock Development, Marine and Blue Economy, and Women Affairs), and representatives of key women farmers' associations such as the Women Farmers Advancement Network (WOFAN) and the Nigeria Women in Agriculture Development and Progressive Initiative (NWAPDI). Secondary data were also reviewed to complement primary findings and provide contextual insights into gender dynamics and agricultural productivity.

3.3 Study Area

The research was conducted in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Abuja, Nigeria, which serves as the country's administrative and policy-making centre. Covering approximately 7,315 square kilometres, the FCT consists of six area councils: Abaji, Bwari, Gwagwalada, Kuje, Kwali, and the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). As the host of central federal ministries and women's agricultural organisations, it provides a strategic location for studying institutional influences on gender inclusion in agriculture. The study focused on four ministries central to agricultural governance and gender mainstreaming—Agriculture and Food Security, Livestock Development, Marine and Blue Economy, and Women Affairs and Social Development. Prominent organisations such as WOFAN and NWAPDI were also included for their active promotion of women's participation in agriculture. The FCT was selected for its accessibility to policymakers and women's groups, making it an ideal setting for examining the institutional and grassroots dimensions of women's agricultural decision-making.

3.4 Target Population

The study's target population consisted of individuals aged 18 years and above who were directly or indirectly involved in agricultural decision-making in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). This included

three key stakeholder groups: policymakers from relevant federal ministries such as Agriculture and Food Security, Livestock Development, Marine and Blue Economy, and Women Affairs and Social Development; members of organized women farmers' associations like WOFAN and NWAPDI advocating for gender inclusiveness in agriculture; and other stakeholders such as agricultural extension workers, cooperative members, NGO representatives, and rural women farmers engaged in various agricultural activities including crop production, livestock, and aquaculture. This diverse categorisation provided a comprehensive representation of both institutional and grassroots perspectives essential for understanding women's roles in agricultural decision-making.

3.5 Sample and Sampling Techniques

The study employed a multi-stage sampling technique to select 285 respondents, ensuring balanced representation across key stakeholder groups involved in agricultural decision-making in the FCT. The sampling process combined stratified, purposive, and random sampling methods. Stratified sampling was used to categorise respondents into three groups—policymakers, organised women farmers' organisations, and other stakeholders—while purposive sampling targeted key informants, including senior government officials and experienced women farmers engaged in gender-sensitive agricultural programs. Random sampling was applied to select women farmers, reducing bias and improving representativeness. Each group contributed 95 respondents, providing equal representation and comparability across categories. The sample size was determined using Cochran's (1977) formula, ensuring statistical validity at the 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error. This structured approach enhanced inclusivity, fairness, and analytical reliability in capturing diverse perspectives on women's roles in agricultural governance.

3.6 Data Collection Methods

Data were obtained from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data collection utilised structured questionnaires, in-depth interviews, and FGDs, while secondary data were sourced from policy documents, academic journals, and institutional reports.

3.6.1 Primary Data Collection

Structured questionnaires were administered via Google Forms, enabling efficient, real-time data collection and minimising logistical constraints (Mishra *et al.*, 2023; Oluwaseun & Chukwuemeka, 2022). The survey captured quantitative information on women's roles, barriers, and institutional influences in agricultural decision-making.

In-depth interviews ($n = 49$) were conducted with policymakers, NGO representatives, and leaders of women farmers' organisations to gain qualitative insights into policy gaps and institutional dynamics. Three FGDs ($n = 30$) were held with women farmers and ministry representatives to explore shared experiences and perceptions regarding gender inclusivity in agricultural governance. The mixed approach enhanced data richness and validity through methodological triangulation (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017; Bryman, 2021).

3.6.2 Secondary Data Collection

Secondary data supplemented primary findings by providing contextual background and policy frameworks. Sources included national gender policy documents, reports from the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), and statistical data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and the Federal Ministry of Agriculture.

3.7 Research Instruments

Three main instruments were used: structured questionnaires for quantitative data; semi-structured interview guides for qualitative inquiry; and FGD protocols to facilitate guided group discussions. Each instrument underwent pilot testing to ensure clarity, relevance, and reliability before full deployment. Expert review by gender and agricultural research specialists enhanced content validity.

3.8 Data Analysis Techniques

Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics via the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive analysis summarised frequencies and means, while regression analysis tested relationships between institutional factors and women's participation.

Qualitative data were analysed thematically following transcription and coding in NVivo, allowing the identification of patterns and insights related to gender roles, empowerment, and policy impact. Findings from both data strands were triangulated to strengthen validity and reliability (Yin, 2018).

3.9 Validity and Reliability

To ensure robustness, content validity was established through expert review, while internal consistency reliability was assessed using Cronbach’s alpha. Triangulation across methods further enhanced reliability. A pilot test was conducted on 20 participants to refine research instruments before full-scale data collection.

3.10 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the University of Abuja Research Ethics Committee. Participants were informed of the study’s purpose and procedures, and written informed consent was secured. Confidentiality, anonymity, and the right to withdraw were assured. Cultural sensitivity was maintained by conducting interviews and FGDs in participants’ preferred languages.

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.0 Introduction

This section presents and analyses data collected through questionnaires and focus group discussions using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Of the 315 distributed questionnaires, 275 were successfully retrieved and analysed, complemented by three focus group discussions involving officials from the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security, the Federal Ministry of Women Affairs, and members of the Nigeria Women in Agriculture Development and Progressive Initiative (NWPADI). The chapter is organized into five key sections: the socio-demographic and economic characteristics of respondents, women’s participation in agricultural decision-making, the role of federal ministries in promoting women’s involvement, challenges hindering women’s access to agricultural decision-making platforms, and the effectiveness of policies designed to enhance women’s participation in agriculture within federal ministries and women farmers’ organizations in the FCT. The analysis draws on both quantitative and qualitative data from the 275 valid responses and 30 qualitative inputs.

4.1 Socio-Demography And Economic Characteristics Of The Respondents

The demographic analysis of respondents provides essential insights into Exploring Women’s Roles in Agricultural Decision-Making: A Case Study of Federal Ministries and Women Farmers’ Groups in Abuja-FCT, Nigeria.

Table 1: Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	96	34.9
Female	179	65.1
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The Table above presents the sex distribution of the respondents. Of the 275 respondents, 65.1% were females and 34.9% were males. Confirming that women play a dominant role in the agricultural space covered by this study. This high representation of women provides a solid foundation for analysing their involvement in agricultural decision-making processes, enabling an in-depth understanding of their roles, challenges, and contributions across both governmental and grassroots agricultural contexts.

Table 2: Age of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18 – 25	71	31.3
26-35	108	47.6
36-45	51	22.5
46-55	42	18.5
56 and above	03	1.3
Total	275	100.0

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above provides the age distribution of the respondents in a study. The largest group was aged 26-35 years, comprising 47.6% of the total. The next largest group was aged 18 - 25 years, with 22.5%, followed by those aged 26 – 45 years, with 22.5%, followed by 46-55 years with 18.5%. A smaller proportion of respondents (1.3%) indicates they are 56 years of age or older. This indicates a youthful population participating in agriculture, which is promising for the long-term sustainability of female engagement in agricultural decision-making. The youthfulness of these women suggests the potential for long-term policy engagement, innovation, and leadership development in the farming sector.

Table 3 Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	137	49.8
Married	130	47.3
Divorced	01	0.4
Widowed	07	2.5
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above presents the respondents' marital status in the study. 49.8% were single, making it the most common marital status. This was followed by married respondents, who made up 47.3%; 2.5% were widowed; and the remaining 0.4% were divorced. This near-equal distribution highlights that women at different stages of family life are involved in agriculture. However, marital status could also influence women's time availability and decision-making autonomy, especially in patriarchal settings. Understanding this dynamic is key to developing inclusive policies that empower all women, regardless of their marital status.

Table 4: Educational Level of the Respondents

Educational	Frequency	Percentage
No Formal Education	00	0.0
Primary	01	0.4
Secondary	24	8.7
Tertiary	250	90.9
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above presents the educational qualifications of the respondents. The largest group, 90.9%, had a tertiary education, followed by 8.7% with secondary education, and the smallest group, 0.4%, had a primary education. This indicates that the women involved in this study are highly literate and capable of engaging with agricultural policies and decision-making structures, as educational qualifications are a critical factor in understanding, contributing to, and influencing institutional and policy frameworks. This suggests that many of the women surveyed are well-equipped to participate meaningfully in agricultural leadership roles.

Table 5: Occupation of the Respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Policy Makers	108	39.3
Farmers Organisation Officer	46	16.7
Extension Worker	20	7.3
NGO Representative - NWAP-DI	22	8.0
Farmer	66	24.0
Student	10	3.6
Others	03	1.1
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above presents the occupations of respondents. The largest group, 39.5% were policymakers. Following this, 24.6% are farmers, 16.7% are farmers' organisation officer, 8.0% are NGO members of Women Farmers' Organisations such as NIWAB and NWAP-DI, reflecting the strong presence of organised female actors within the sector, 7.3% are extension workers, 3.6% are students, and the least respondents were those who engages in other occupation with 1.1%. The composition of respondents underscores the multi-layered nature of participation in agriculture and climate resilience. The strong representation of women in both formal organisations and grassroots stakeholders demonstrates their active involvement at various levels of the value chain. This diverse occupational mix not only enriches the survey's knowledge base but also strengthens the potential for inclusive, context-driven decision-making. The presence of women in these formal and informal sectors of agriculture suggests that they contribute at various levels of the agricultural value chain from production to policy. This diversity enhances women's potential to influence decision-making from multiple vantage points.

Table 6: Length of Experience of the Respondents in Agriculture

Experience	Frequency	Percentage
0-5	134	49.1
6-10	61	22.3
11-15	38	13.9
16 years and above	42	15.3
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above presents the respondents' experience in agriculture. The largest group, 49.1%, had 0-5 years of experience in the agricultural sector, followed by 6-10 years (22.3%), 16 years and above (15.3%), and 11-15 years (13.9%). This implies that there are also seasoned women whose experiences and institutional memory could be leveraged for mentoring and leadership development. The growing influx of new entrants indicates expanding interest in and inclusion of women in the agricultural sector, likely driven by empowerment initiatives or economic necessity.

4.2: Women's Participation in Agricultural Decision-Making

Using a quantitative approach, this utilised the frequency and breakdown of the respondents' awareness and understanding of women's participation in Agricultural decision-making in FCT, Abuja, under the following subheadings.

Table 7: Respondents' Awareness of any Federal Ministries Involved in Agricultural Decision Making in FCT Abuja

Awareness	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	209	76.0
No	66	24.0
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above provides information on awareness of any Federal Ministries involved in Agricultural decision-making in FCT Abuja. 76.0% confirmed that they are aware of the Federal Ministries involved in Agricultural Decision Making in FCT Abuja, while 24.0% indicated that they are not aware of any Such Ministries. This high level of awareness is a positive sign, as it reflects the increasing visibility of federal institutions and their roles among women farmers and professionals. However, the existing awareness gap also underscores the need for improved communication and engagement strategies to ensure that all women are informed and equipped to participate in decision-making processes, particularly those from marginalised or rural backgrounds.

Table 8: Respondents' Views on Whether Women are Adequately Involved in the Agricultural Decision-Making Process in FCT

Involvement	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	138	50.2
No	82	29.8
Not Sure	55	20.0
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above provides information on the extent of women's involvement in agricultural decision-making in the FCT. 50.2% indicated that they are adequately involved in farm decisions, while 29.8% said no, and 20.0% said they are not sure. This mixed perception suggests that although some progress has been made in including women, there are still significant concerns about the depth and visibility of their involvement. The uncertainty among a notable number of respondents highlights the possible lack of transparency or communication around women's actual roles in these processes.

Table 9: Respondents' Views on Whether Women Actively Participate in Decision Making in FCT

Participation	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	204	74.5
No	44	16.1
Not Sure	27	9.8
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above provides information on women's active participation in decision-making in FCT. 74.5% indicated that they participate in decision-making, while 16.1% said no, and 9.8% said they are not sure. This shows that while national or federal involvement might be perceived as limited, many institutions or grassroots organisations are fostering inclusive environments where women's voices are heard. This is an encouraging trend and lays the foundation for influencing broader policy changes from the bottom up.

Table 10: Respondents' View on Specific Programs or Policies to Promote Women's Participation in Agricultural Decision Making in FCT

Specific Programs	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	169	61.5
No	42	15.3
Not Sure	64	23.3
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above provides information on whether there are specific Programs or policies to promote women's participation in agriculture in FCT. 61.5% indicated that there are particular programs or policies to encourage women's involvement in agriculture, while 23.3% said they are not sure, and 15.3% said no. This implies that although supportive policies may exist, they may not be widely disseminated or translated into actionable initiatives at the community level.

Table 11: Respondents' View on the Significance of Women's Contributions to Agricultural Decision Making in FCT

Significant	Frequency	Percentage
Least Significant	19	6.8
Fairy Significant	50	18.0
Significant	97	34.9
More Significant	53	19.1
Most significant	57	20.5
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above provides information on the significance of women's contributions to agricultural decision-making in FCT. 34.9% indicated that women are substantial to agricultural decision-making in FCT; 20.5% indicated most significant; 19.1% showed more significant; 18.0% indicated fairly substantial; and 6.8% indicated least significant. This strong, positive outlook reflects growing recognition of the value women bring to agricultural governance and underscores the need for their inclusion in strategic discussions and policy formulation.

Table 12: Respondents' View on the Level of Influence Women have in Shaping Agricultural Policies in FCT

Level	Frequency	Percentage
High	75	27.4
Low	53	19.3
Moderate	144	52.6
None	03	1.1
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above provides information on the extent of women's influence in shaping agricultural policies in FCT. 52.6% indicated that the level of influence women have in shaping agrarian policies is moderate, 27.4% indicated high, 19.3% showed low, and 1.1% did not take any position. This distribution suggests that while women are seen as having some impact, there is still room to elevate their influence and authority within key decision-making bodies, especially at the federal level.

4.3: Role of Federal Ministries In Promoting Women's Participation In Agriculture Decision-Making Processes

Using a quantitative approach, this utilised the frequency and breakdown of respondents' views on the role of Federal Ministries in promoting women's participation in the Agricultural Decision-Making Process, under the subheadings below.

Table 13: Respondents' Views on Whether Federal Ministries Adequately Involve Women in Agricultural Governance in FCT

Involvement	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	31	11.3
Agree	114	41.6
Neutral	76	27.7
Disagree	47	17.2
Strongly Disagree	06	2.2
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

Table 13 presents respondents' views on whether federal ministries adequately involve women in agricultural governance within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The results show that 31 respondents (11.3%) strongly agreed and 114 respondents (41.6%) agreed, indicating that a majority (52.9%) believe that federal ministries are making efforts to include women in agricultural governance. However, 76 respondents (27.7%) remained neutral, suggesting uncertainty or limited awareness about the extent of women's involvement. Meanwhile, 47 respondents (17.2%) disagreed, and six respondents (2.2%) strongly disagreed, representing 19.4% who believe that women are not adequately involved. Overall, the findings suggest moderate inclusion of women in agricultural governance, but the high proportion of neutral and dissenting opinions indicates that more deliberate policies and institutional efforts are needed to strengthen women's participation and influence in agricultural decision-making processes in the FCT.

Table 14: Respondents' View on Whether Women Contribute to Agricultural Policy Formulation Recognised in FCT

Using a quantitative approach and utilising the frequency and breakdown of respondents on whether women contribute to agricultural policy formulation in FCT, the following response was obtained.

Contributions	Frequency	Percentage
Always	64	23.4
Sometimes	132	48.2
Rarely	70	25.5
Never	09	3.3
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

Table 14 presents respondents' views on whether women's contributions to agricultural policy formulation are recognised in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The results indicate that 64 respondents (23.4%) believe women's contributions are consistently recognised, while a larger proportion—132 respondents (48.2%)—stated that women's input is only sometimes acknowledged. Additionally, 70 respondents (25.5%) reported that women's contributions are rarely recognised, and nine respondents (3.3%) reported that they are never recognised. This distribution suggests that although women occasionally participate in agricultural policy formulation, their input is not consistently valued or institutionalised. The dominance of the "sometimes" and "rarely" responses (73.7%) highlights the partial and irregular inclusion of women in policymaking processes, indicating the need for stronger institutional frameworks and gender-sensitive policies to ensure that women's voices are systematically integrated and appreciated in agricultural governance within the FCT.

Table 15: Respondents' Views on Whether They Have Attended Any Program or Platform Organised by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture in FCT

Using a quantitative approach that utilised frequency and a breakdown of respondents' attendance at programs or platforms organised by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture in the FCT, the following information was obtained.

Programs	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	150	54.5
No	125	45.5
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above provides information on whether respondents have attended any program or platform organised by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture in the FCT. 54.5% indicated that they had participated in a program or platform organised by the Ministry of Agriculture before, while 45.5% said they had not. This emphasises the need for federal agencies to improve outreach and inclusivity in their program planning and execution.

4.4: Challenges Faced by Women in Agriculture Decision Making

Using a quantitative approach that utilises frequency and respondent breakdowns of the obstacles preventing women from participating in decision-making in FCT, the following information was obtained from respondents.

Table 16: Respondents' Views on Obstacles Preventing Women from Participating in Decision Making in FCT

Obstacles	Frequency	Percentage
Socio-Cultural Norms	133	48.4
Limited access to resources	38	13.8
Lack of Education or Skill	38	13.8
Underrepresentation in Leadership Roles	66	24.0
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

Table 16 presents respondents' views on the key obstacles preventing women from participating in agricultural decision-making in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The findings reveal that socio-cultural norms are the most significant barrier, as indicated by 133 respondents (48.4%), suggesting that traditional gender roles and societal expectations continue to limit women's involvement in governance and leadership. Underrepresentation in leadership roles was also a significant challenge, cited by 66 respondents (24.0%), reflecting institutional barriers and gender bias within decision-making structures. Additionally, limited access to resources and lack of education or skills each accounted for 38 responses (13.8%), highlighting economic and capacity-related constraints that hinder women's effective participation. Overall, the data suggest that while structural issues such as education and resource access are important, deeply rooted socio-cultural norms remain the most critical factor restricting women's full participation in agricultural decision-making in the FCT.

Table 17: Respondents' Views on the biggest Challenges Women face in Agricultural Decision-Making Platforms in FCT

Using a quantitative approach that utilised the frequency and breakdown of respondents' responses to the most significant challenges women face in agricultural decision-making platforms in FCT, the following information was obtained.

Challenges	Frequency	Percentage
Socio-Cultural Norms	54	19.6
Lack of resources	119	43.3
Lack of Leadership Roles	66	24.0
Others	12	4.4
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above identifies the biggest challenges women face in agricultural decision-making platforms in FCT. 43.3% indicated a lack of resources, including land, capital, and extension services, as the most significant constraint, followed by a lack of leadership roles (24.0%), and socio-cultural norms. 4.4% of the respondents indicated other challenges, such as integrity issues. This aligns with broader development research that identifies access to resources as a persistent barrier to female empowerment in agriculture, including time burdens, political exclusion, and internal organisational dynamics that were not predefined. Interestingly, socio-cultural norms again emerged as a key issue, reinforcing their pervasive influence on women's ability to engage equally.

Table 18: Respondents' Views on Whether Women Face Discrimination in Accessing the Agricultural Decision-Making Platform in FCT

Using a quantitative approach that used frequency and respondent breakdowns on whether women face discrimination in accessing the agricultural decision-making platform in FCT, the following information was obtained.

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above provides information on whether women face discrimination in accessing the agricultural decision-making platform in FCT. 60.0% of respondents indicated that women sometimes face discrimination in accessing the agricultural decision-making platform in FCT, followed by 28.4% who

Existence of Discrimination	Frequency	Percentage
Always	78	28.4
Sometimes	165	60.0
Rarely	10	3.6
Never	22	8.0
Total	275	100

indicated that women always face discrimination, 8.0% who indicated that women never face discrimination, and 3.6% who indicated that women rarely face discrimination. These findings underscore

that gender bias is not only systemic but also frequent, limiting equitable participation in governance and policy-related spaces.

4.5: Policy Effectiveness

Table 19: Respondents' View on Whether Gender-Inclusive Policies are effectively implemented in the FCT

Using a quantitative approach that utilised frequency and a breakdown of respondents on whether gender-inclusive policies are effectively implemented in FCT, the following information was obtained.

Effectiveness of Gender Inclusive Policies	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	31	11.3
Agree	108	39.3
Neutral	97	35.3
Disagree	32	11.6
Strongly Disagree	07	2.5
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

Table 19 presents respondents' views on whether gender-inclusive policies are effectively implemented in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The results indicate that a majority of respondents — 31 (11.3%) who strongly agreed and 108 (39.3%) who agreed — believe that gender-inclusive policies are being implemented to some extent in the region. However, 97 respondents (35.3%) remained neutral, suggesting uncertainty or mixed perceptions about the actual effectiveness of these policies in practice. Meanwhile, 32 respondents (11.6%) disagreed and 7 (2.5%) strongly disagreed, indicating that a notable minority perceive the implementation as poor or ineffective. Overall, the findings imply that while there is a general acknowledgement of efforts toward gender inclusivity in policy execution, significant gaps persist in consistency, awareness, and enforcement—suggesting that more concrete actions are needed to translate gender policies into meaningful outcomes in the FCT agricultural sector.

Table 20: Respondents' Views on Whether Farmers Benefit Equally from Agricultural Programs and Policies in the FCT

Benefitted Equally	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	94	34.2
No	104	37.8
Not Sure	77	28.0
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above provides information on whether farmers benefit equally from Agricultural programs and policies in FCT. 37.8% of respondents answered no, 34.2% answered yes, and 28.0% were unsure whether farmers benefit equally from agricultural programs and policies in the FCT. This uncertainty and near-even split indicate that although some progress may be underway, the actual outcomes of gender-inclusive interventions are not uniformly experienced or understood across the sector. This suggests a potential gap between policy intent and grassroots realities.

Table 21: Respondents' Views on Whether Women's Organisations Are Effective in Advocating for Gender Sensitive Agricultural Policies in the FCT

Using a quantitative approach, which utilised the frequency and breakdown of respondents' responses on whether women's organisations are effective in advocating for gender-sensitive agricultural policies in FCT, the following information was obtained.

Effective	Frequency	Percentage
Highly Effective	71	25.8
Moderate Effective	171	62.2
Not Ineffective	33	12.0
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above provides information on the effectiveness of women’s organisations in advocating for Gender-Sensitive Agricultural Policies in the FCT. 62.2% indicated that women’s organisations are moderately effective, while 25.8% indicated they are highly effective, and 12.0% indicated they are not effective. This demonstrates that these organisations play a crucial intermediary role, though their influence may still be developing or constrained by external limitations such as access to decision-makers or funding. Awareness of policy tools is crucial for implementation.

Table 22: Respondents' Awareness of Gender Inclusivity in Agricultural Policies, such as the National Gender Policy in the FCT

Using a quantitative approach that utilised the frequency and breakdown of respondents’ awareness of gender inclusivity in agricultural policies, such as the National Gender Policy in the FCT, the following information was obtained.

Awareness	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	165	60.0
No	110	40.0
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above provides information on respondents' awareness of gender inclusivity in Agricultural Policies, such as the National Gender Policy in FCT. A majority of the respondents, 60.0%, indicated that they are aware of gender inclusivity in Agricultural policies, while 40.0% disagreed with the above view that they are not aware. This demonstrates that these organisations play a crucial intermediary role, though their influence may still be developing or constrained by external limitations such as access to decision-makers or funding. Awareness of policy tools is crucial for implementation.

Table 23: Respondents' Views on Whether these Policies have Improved Women’s Participation in Decision Making in FCT

Using a quantitative approach that utilised the frequency and breakdown of respondents' responses on whether policies such as the National Gender Policy in FCT have improved women’s participation in decision-making in FCT, the following information was obtained.

Improvement	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	180	65.5
No	95	34.5
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The table above provides information on whether the listed policies have improved women’s participation in decision-making in FCT. A majority of respondents (65.5%) indicated that these policies have improved women’s participation in decision-making in FCT. In comparison, 34.5% indicated no, suggesting that, despite awareness and policy advocacy, actual participation may still be hindered by cultural, institutional, or logistical challenges.

Table 24: Respondents' Views on Whether Policy Frameworks like the National Agricultural Transformation Policy (NATIP) are effectively implemented in FCT

Using a quantitative approach that utilised the frequency and breakdown of respondents' responses on whether policies like the National Agricultural Transformation Policy (NATIP) are effectively implemented in FCT, the following information was obtained.

Improvement	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	160	58.2
No	115	41.8
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

Table 24 presents respondents’ views on whether policy frameworks, such as the National Agricultural Transformation Policy (NATIP), are effectively implemented in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Out

of 275 respondents, 160 (58.2%) affirmed that these policies are effectively implemented, while 115 (41.8%) disagreed. This indicates that a majority of respondents perceive some level of effectiveness in the implementation of NATIP and similar frameworks. However, the relatively high proportion of negative responses suggests that challenges still exist in policy execution, monitoring, and impact delivery. Overall, the findings imply that while NATIP has made progress toward agricultural transformation goals in the FCT, further efforts are needed to strengthen its implementation mechanisms and ensure equitable benefits for all stakeholders, particularly women farmers.

4.6.1 DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The study's findings reveal that women in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) are increasingly aware of and engaged in agricultural decision-making processes facilitated by federal ministries. Approximately 76% of respondents acknowledged awareness of federal involvement in agricultural governance, suggesting progress toward gender inclusion. This awareness is critical, as it enables women to advocate for access to resources such as credit, farm inputs, and extension services, thereby directly enhancing household food security and reducing poverty. The study aligns with Nwachukwu and Anuforo (2022), who emphasised that public sector interventions have made strides toward gender-sensitive agricultural policies, although challenges persist in their grassroots implementation. Similarly, the study found that 74.5% of women actively participate in decision-making at various levels, reinforcing the idea that inclusive participation not only promotes gender equity but also improves agricultural productivity and nutritional outcomes. Nonetheless, institutional gaps, cultural barriers, and weak coordination among ministries continue to limit the full realisation of these benefits (Akpoti et al., 2021; Olagunju et al., 2020; Adekola et al., 2022).

The study further highlights that while many women (76%) are aware of existing agricultural programs and policies designed to support their inclusion, there remains a significant need for broader knowledge dissemination and sensitisation. Awareness of such programs is essential, as women without this knowledge are unable to access or benefit from opportunities in agricultural development. Strengthening awareness through education, media engagement, and extension services could enhance women's ability to utilise available support systems and influence governance processes. Despite their contributions, nearly half of the respondents (48.2%) indicated that women's input in agricultural policy formulation is only "sometimes" recognised. This inconsistency undermines their confidence and reduces long-term engagement in governance. The findings, therefore, underscore the importance of institutionalising women's representation and ensuring their perspectives are integrated into final agricultural policies to foster equitable and sustainable development.

The findings also reveal that social-cultural norms, limited resources, and underrepresentation in leadership positions remain significant obstacles to women's decision-making in agriculture. Although gender-inclusive policies such as the National Gender Policy and the National Agricultural Transformation Implementation Policy (NATIP) are reportedly gaining traction in the FCT, with 39.3% of respondents affirming their effectiveness, systemic and structural inequalities hinder their full impact. This resonates with Akinyele et al. (2020), who noted that women's limited land ownership and restricted access to financial and technological resources perpetuate gender disparities. The study concludes that while the trajectory toward gender equity in agricultural decision-making is positive, more deliberate and coordinated efforts are required to close existing gaps. This includes ensuring that policies are effectively implemented, culturally adaptive, and supported by sustained advocacy, training, and institutional reform to empower women as equal partners in agricultural governance.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

The study concludes that women play a pivotal yet underrecognized role in Nigeria's agricultural sector, particularly in decision-making processes within federal ministries and women farmers' organisations in the FCT. Despite their substantial contributions to food production, poverty alleviation, and household welfare, systemic gender inequalities continue to limit their influence in agricultural governance. The findings revealed that while awareness of government involvement in agricultural programs is high,

women's participation in decision-making remains constrained by socio-cultural norms, inadequate education, limited access to resources, and underrepresentation in leadership positions. Nonetheless, the increasing implementation of gender-inclusive policies such as the National Gender Policy and the National Agricultural Transformation Implementation Policy (NATIP) signifies progress toward equitable participation. For sustainable agricultural development, it is essential to integrate women's voices in policy formulation, planning, and implementation at all levels.

The study recommends that the government at all levels institutionalise gender-responsive agricultural governance through deliberate policy actions. This includes conducting gender impact assessments before implementing agricultural programs to ensure equitable benefits for women and mandating at least 30–40% female representation in agricultural boards, cooperatives, and development committees. Furthermore, there is a need for capacity-building initiatives, awareness campaigns, and education programs to enhance women's knowledge of existing agricultural policies and opportunities. Partnerships with NGOs, community-based organisations, and traditional leaders should be strengthened to challenge discriminatory norms and promote women's leadership in agriculture. Finally, improving women's access to land ownership, credit facilities, training, and technology will not only empower them but also enhance agricultural productivity, food security, and overall national development.

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